

THE DIFFERENCE OF LEARNING APPROACH INFLUENCES TOWARDS SHOOTING THREE POINT OF BASKETBALL

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Abstract:

This study aims to find out, (1) the difference influence between approaching methods of repetitive and progressive learning towards the shooting three-point in Basketball. (2) The difference of basketball shooting three points at students who have low and high of basic movement skill. (3) The possibility interaction exists on the methods of learning approaches and basic movement skill against basketball shooting three points. Study methods used in this study is an experimentation method using 2×2 factorial designs. The sample used in this study are 36 people (9 people with high basic movement skill and 9 people with low basic movement using progressive approach and 9 people with high basic movement skill and 9 people with low basic movement skill using repetitive learning approach). The technique of data analysis used in this study is a technique of variants analysis (ANAVA) design factorial 2×2 at $\alpha = 0.05$. When the value of F is obtained (F_0) the analysis is significant then continued with range test Hewman-Keuls. The results showed that, (1) $F_{\text{analysis}} = 1.30 < F_{\text{table}} = 4.15$ with level of significance of 5%. Thus the result of the zero hypotheses (H_0) is received. (2) $F_{\text{analysis}} = 36.90 > F_{\text{table}} = 4.15$. Thus the result of the zero hypotheses (H_0) is denied. (3) $F_{\text{analysis}} = 7.06 > F_{\text{table}} = 4.15$. Thus the result of the zero hypotheses (H_0) is denied. (1) There is no significant difference between the approaches of repetitive and progressive learning against the results of three point shooting skills at the basketball game. (2) There is a significant difference in the skill of learning results of three-point between the students who have high and low basic movement skill. (3) There is a significant influence of

interaction between the difference of learning and level of movement skill toward learning the result of three points shooting on the basketball game.

Keywords: repetitive learning approach, a progressive learning approach, shooting three points

1. Introduction

The basketball game is a game that needs a velocity, a player is required always moving while they do basic techniques, try to enter the ball to the rival's ring as many as possible without getting interference from the rival and try to keep their ring from rival's attack. Enter the ball into the ring can be done with shooting. According to Prusak (2007:61) "*there is some kind of shooting such as lay-up, free throw, three points shot and jump shot.*"

The basic technique in basketball which has major contribution to support victory in the game is shot three points or shooting three points. Shooting three points (shooting three points) is the most widely-shot produce points compared to another shot such as the free throw and layup in the basketball game. However from the tactics point of view, shooting three points is expected attack that can deliver score or points from a distance without going closer to the rival's defences. "*Shooting is the most popular basic skills for players of all ages and levels*" (Donovan, 2010:37). Paye (2013) argues that "*shooting the basketball is one of the skills in the basketball sport and it can be increased during doing the exercise*". While according to Kosasih (2008:46) says that "*the technique of shooting (the shot) was started from the position of the legs are ready (triple threat position), the target is the ring and should focus our gaze to the ring, hold on the ball with steady and widening the fingers comfortably, supporting hand is used only to maintain the balance holding the ball before the ball is thrown towards the basketball hoop*". In doing the shooting three point according to Krause, et al (1936:74) "*there are some terms related to shooting techniques in basketball that need to be introduced to the players from early, like B E E F (Balance, Eyes, Elbow, the Follow Through)*".

The fact that occurs today, the teachers are faced with time limitations as well as the inadequacy of the equipment that inappropriate to the number of students who will be trained while there are a lot of the material will be trained to the students. This problem is certainly one of those due to the limitations of the skill and quality of the basketball teacher or coach in managing and modifying the approach to learning. The learning approach is one way to improve sports achievements. The selection of the learning approach should also consider the timing of the skill of facilities and

equipment needed. The necessity for an efficient learning approach in shooting three-point exercise was troubled by some of the reasons: *"first, the efficiency to save the time, energy, or cost. Second, the efficient methods will allow the players to master a higher skill level"* (Lutan, 1988:26).

Learning approach is an approach way to the presentation of learning material that is systematically done to encourage the achievement of the teaching objectives in a process to make people learn. According to Hidayatullah (2009:161) *"in order to the learning can be fun for the learners, then the teacher should be good and creative in a package the material so that learners interested in learning, one of the way that can be done by the teacher is doing various learning approach"*. Nadisah (1992:96) said that *"learning an approach will appropriate when it can increase the effectiveness and efficiency"*. Learning the process, besides starting with a good plan, supported with learning environment with excellent communication is also have to be supported by the strategy development that able to make the students learn. According to Majid (2008:111) *"management of learning is a process of organising interactions with educators, learners and learning resources in an environment of learning, good learning should be able to deliver successful experiences to participants"*. According to Hidayatullah (2009:85), successful experience in question is *"the existence of a feeling of fun and boast about learners as a result has been successfully completed or solves the problems"*.

Learning approach is one of basic learning strategy in teaching and learning process, it is used to achieve the goal. *"The successful of goal accomplishment that is specified by the skills of the teacher in providing guidance and the observation of the movement through the stages of perception, preparedness, social interactions, habitual movement, complex movement, and the adjustment to the movement pattern and creativity"*. (Winkel, 1999:44). Learning/exercise in basketball games aims to make students can master the shooting three point skills; this movement skill could be interpreted as the skill to perform the duties of a particular movement with good and right. The better mastery of movement skills, then the implementation will be more efficient. Movement skills are one of movement categories that require coordination and control of the body as a whole or part of the body. Movement skills are a movement that meets certain criteria. Superman (2000:56) States that there are three skilled movement indicator that is, *"1) is effective, means that appropriate with the desired product, 2) efficient means in accordance with the process that is supposed to do, 3) Adaptive, means that accordance with the situation and environmental conditions where movement is done"*.

The right learning approach in the learning process of playing basketball is should be able to engender a sense of pleased at students also provide opportunities for the teachers in utilizing existing facilities to the maximum so that there is no reason for

teachers to say that there is the delay in learning process is due to the less of facility and equipment sport available in school. The type of learning approach that also used to shooting three point learning process in basketball, among others is a repetitive and progressive method. This study will discuss skill learning using repetitive and progressive method more detail. *"Repetitive method is a learning method which students learning some section until they mastered then combine it with another new section and they learned and practice it together until they mastered it. This procedure is followed by each remaining section until all section can be practice as a whole"* (Christina & Corcos, 1988:77). Repetitive learning approach learns every new movement part, directly coupled to the element movement that has been owned before, only through explanation or example without mastery of movement first. In this method, students are given a new element of the technique of shooting three points in basketball, then directly coupled to the element movement that has been owned and taught before. According to Rooijackers (1990:19) that is *"the repetition of information would strengthen the skill of the student to remember it"*.

Progressive learning approach is the way that is done to minimize the problem of learning activities that are not transferred to the whole. Ma'mun (2000:91) says that *"in the progressive method, the complex skills are presented separately, but these activities are integrated into the larger part and whole."* According to Magill (2001:34) that *"in the progressive method students is practising the first section as an independent unit and then studied the second section separately and then the first and second section together, so that each part of an independent progressively joined in larger part."* According to Christina & Corcos (1988:76) that *"the progressive method is a method used in learning where students learn one section until mastered then learn another section until further mastering, practised together until it's mastered, then the third section are taught individually after the part was conquered. The third section combined and practised together until it's mastered"*.

2. Method

Study methods used in this study is an experimentation method using 2 x 2 factorial designs. The sample used in this study is as much as 36 boy's participants from basketball extracurricular of SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta. That participant then divided into two groups, group one is consist of 18 people with high basic movement and 18 people from the low basic movement group. The next group of basic high and low movement given instructional approach with progressive treatment (9 people high basic movement and 9 people low basic movement) and repetitive learning approach (9 people high basic movement and 9 people low basic movement). To know the success

of the process of learning approaches to increase shooting three points the studier give pre-test, treatment and post-test to the participant.

The technique of data analysis used in this study is variants analysis technique (ANAVA) factorial design 2×2 at $\alpha = 0.05$. If the value of F is obtained (F_o) then the significant analysis is continued with the range test Hewman-Keuls.

3. Results

Table 1: The result from two line ANOVA the using learning approach and basic movement skill in basketball Shooting Three Point

Variants Source	dk	JK	RJK	F_o	$F_{table\ 5\%}$
A (learning approach)	1	9	9	1,30	
B (basic movement skill)	1	256	256	36,90	4,15
AB (interaction)	1	49	49	7,06	
Dalam group (D) Residue	32	222	6,9375	-	-
Total	36	536	-	-	-

1. The test result showed that the value of $F_{analysis} = 1.30 < F_{table} = 4.15$ to a significance level of 5%. Thus, the result of the zero hypotheses (H_0) is received. It means that there is no significant difference between learning by using repetitive and progressive approach.
2. The results of the study showed that the value of $F_{analysis} = 36.90 > F_{tabel} = 4.15$. Thus, the result of the zero hypotheses (H_0) is denied. It means that students who have high movement have three point shooting skills improvement on the game were different with students who have low movement capabilities.
3. The results of the study showed that the value of $F_{analysis} = 7.06 > F_{tabel} = 4.15$. Thus, the result of the zero hypotheses (H_0) is denied. It means there is significant influence interaction between the types of learning approach to shooting three point game on a basketball game and the level of movement skill.

4. Discussion

A. The difference in the influence of Progressive and Repetitive Learning Approach toward Basketball Shooting Three Point Skills Learning Outcomes. Based on first hypothesis testing it turns out there is no significant difference between the Groups of

students who get a progressive learning approach and a group of students who get repetitive learning approach, to increase their skill to do shooting three points in a basketball game. The difference in the approach used during the learning is affected to enthusiasm, motivation, the creativity of different students, so as to obtain results in the mastery of movement skills shooting three points. The Group provided the treatment learning shooting three points with progressive and repetitive approaches have a different influence on the three point shooting skills improvement in a basketball game. The group who got the treatment of repetitive learning approach turns out to have a shooting skill enhancement is slightly better than the group that received the treatment of learning with the progressive approach.

B. The difference result of learning skill shooting three points on a basketball game between the student who has high movement skill and low movement skill. Based on the second hypothesis test there is real different influence between a group of student with high movement skill and low movement skill toward the skill improvement of shooting three points in a basketball game. It turns out that there is a real difference influence between a group of students with a high-movement skill and the low movement skill towards the results of three point shooting skills on the basketball game. A group of students with high-movement capabilities has increased three-point shooting skills on the basketball game higher than groups of students with low movement capabilities. The students with high movement skill have a higher potential than students with low movement capabilities. The movement skill is a basic to create student's skill. A good movement skill will support the readiness of the student to do skill learning. A high movement skill can accelerate the process of mastering the skill of movement which is studied.

C. The influence of the interaction between the Learning Approach with the movement skill towards the skill learning results of Shooting Three Point on the basketball game. Based on the results of the study, students who have high-movement skill will have a great improvement on shooting three-point skills if they are given repetitive approach learning, whereas students who have the low movement skill will be effective when given with a progressive learning approach. The effectiveness use of learning approach to shooting three points on the game was influenced by the skill level of movement which belonged to students.

5. Conclusions

Based on the results of the study and the results of data analysis that has been done, the following conclusions can be obtained.

1. There is no significant difference between the approaches of repetitive and progressive learning against the results of shooting three point skills learned on the basketball game. The application of learning with repetitive approach apparently would give influence on the three point shooting skills are better than the progressive approach to learning.
2. There is a significant difference in the results of three-point shooting skill learning between the students who have high and low movement capabilities. The improvement skill of Shooting Three-point on the basketball game on the students who have the skill of high movement better than low-movement has the skill.
3. There was a significant interaction between the influence the approach of learning and skill level of movement towards the results of shooting three point skills learned on the basketball game.
 - a) Students who have the high movement skill are more appropriate with repetitive approach learning.
 - b) Students with low movement skill more appropriate with a progressive approach to learning.

6. Suggestions

Based on the result of this study, then for the teacher or sports coach especially basketball is given such of these suggestions.

1. In an effort to improve skills, particularly the shooting three point skills is a must use the right learning approach in accordance with the development of the students.
2. Learning with the repetitive parts of the approach have a better influence in improving the skills of shooting three points in a basketball game so that teachers and coaches prefer learning with the repetitive parts of the approach in an attempt to improve the results of three point shooting basketball for their students.
3. It is recommended that Teachers develop repetitive parts of the learning approaches in order to improve learning outcomes skills of basketball shooting three points.
4. The application of the use of a learning approach to improve the skills of shooting three points in basketball game need to pay attention to the movement skill factor.

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